

IMMUNOGISTOCHEMICAL CHANGES OF THE THYMUSIS OF PREMATURE STILLBORN INFANTS

Mahkamov N.J.

Andijan State Medical Institute,
DSc., associate professor
nosirzonmahkamov 5@ gmail . com Andijan the city

Yuldashev Z.N.

Andijan State Medical Institute
independent researcher ziyoyidding@gmail. com Andijan city .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14264193>

Abstract: In this period, CD 3, CD 4, Ki 67 markers were studied in order to study the dynamics of T-lymphocytes according to the cellular composition of the morphofunctional active centers in the thymus of stillborn babies . Delays in morphological development in the thyroid gland: the cortex of the thymus is characterized by the fact that it occupies a very small area of the medulla in terms of width, and there are almost no lymphocytes. As the main morphological substrate of these changes, the reticuloepithelial cells of the thymus cortical layer are small in size, the desmosomes are short and thick, there are many sparse fibrous structures connecting the desmosomes, and the perivascular areas of the cortical layer show that the hematohistiogenic barrier has become functionally impaired. .

Key words : thymus, immunohistochemistry, involution, immunodeficiency, necrosis, apoptosis.

Relevance of the problem: In perinatal pathologies, antenatal death mainly develops together with processes of infectious and non-infectious etiology and manifests itself in the form of fetal immaturity, asphyxia, birth trauma, pneumopathies, perinatal blood circulation in the brain, and hemorrhagic disease of newborns.

In the world, newborns or perinatal pathologies account for 1-4% of every 1000 births, and it is understood that the fetus is stillborn due to intrauterine infection. It is the development of the immune system that has a major impact on health, especially during pregnancy, early childhood, and even throughout life (Hertz-Picciotto et al., 2008). There is increasing evidence revealing a link between interventions during the perinatal period and immune system disorders in offspring later in life (Yang et al., 2014).

Discussion and result : The first 28-33 weeks of the antenatal period are characterized by the relative formation of differentiation in the members of the immune system, in premature births, the relative formation of viability and

resistance to infection in infants, and the stable and highly developed proliferative processes in the thymus and bone marrow. In this group, the positive expression of the Ki 67 marker is at a high level, and it is also detected in the parenchyma and mesenchymal cells of the cortex and medulla of the thymus.

Although the degree of differentiation is higher compared to the above group, the positively expressed cells are mainly fibroblasts, macrophages, histiocytes, reticulocytes and T lymphocytes.

Although the lymphocytes present in the parenchyma of the incompletely formed thymus, that is, the primary immune organ, have high proliferative indicators, as a result of increased formation, Ki The positive expression of marker 67 at 200x magnification was shown with an average of 27.65% in the control group, while in this group it was found to be around 34%. According to the immunohistochemical aspects, carried out in order to determine the T-helper subpopulation of lymphocytes through the SD4 marker, it was found that the level of positive expression was very low. It is the very small number of T-helpers that produce immunostimulating factors that tickle T-killers in the thymus cortex and medulla, confirming the lack of differentiation towards autologous tissue tolerance.

Low positive expression in thymus tissue examined for SD 3 and SD 4 markers means that SD 3 is impaired in lymphocyte differentiation and a small number of T helpers with SD 4 markers are formed, resulting in a sharp decrease in immunodeficiency and resistance to infection. In our study, it was confirmed in the clinical anamnestic data of antenatally dead babies whose mother was an infection carrier and all stillbirths in which the fetus had an intrauterine infection.

References used:

1. Biloshapka V. A. i dr. Modern aspects of pathomorphology of congenital cytomegalovirus infection in children in the first year of life (a practical case) //Mediko-sotsialnye problemy semi. - 2021. - T. 26. – no. 2. - S. 99-104.
2. Borodin, Yu.I. Peripheral lymphoid structure: formation and function / Yu.I. Borodin, O.V. Gorchakova, V.N. Gorchakov // Morphology. – 2016. – T. 150, No. 4.– S.90–96.
3. Bocharova O.A., Karpova R.V., Bocharov E.V., Vershinskaya A.A., dr. b2 - integrin LFA-1, MAC-1 - mishen dlya usileniya protiv opukholi./ / Rossiysky bioterapevtichesky zurnal. 2020;19(1):53–8.
4. Bos n V.Yu., Verbitskaya A.I., Solomin Yu.A. Sravnitel'naya otsenka dannyx ultrazhenkovogo i sektsiionnogo issledovaniya vilochkovoy zhelezyu detey

//Ультразвуковая диагностика в акушерстве, гинекологии и педиатрии. No. 3.S. 40-47.

5. Bubnova N. V. i dr. Изменение клеточного состава тимуса крыс через 90 дней после введения уретана на фоне приема селена //Journal анатомии и гистопатологии. - 2024. - Т. 13. – no. 1. – S. 19-27.

6. Verbitskaya A.I., Solokhin Yu.A., Nazarova N.F. Особенности эхографии вилочковой железы у детей в личные разрастные периоды //Ультразвуковая и функциональная диагностика. 2001. No. 3. S. 34-39.

7. Volkov V.G., Kastor M.V. Современные взгляды на проблему классификации и определения причин мертворождения // Российский вестник акушер-гинекология. 2020. Т. 20. No. 3. S. 29-3.

8. Galeeva E.N. Характерные особенности становления топографии ряда органов иммунной системы человека в раннем репродуктивном периоде онтогенеза // Вестник новых медицинских технологий, 2011. Т. 18 No. 2. S. 489-492.

9. Galeeva E. N. Morphological characteristics of the functional zone of the thymus of a human being in the middle reproductive period of ontogeny // Orenburg medical journal. - 2015. - Т. 3. – no. 2 (10). - S. 15-19.

